

CLASSIFICATION OF MEANS LINKING VERBS TO VERBS IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19550173>

Abstract: *This article is part of a larger comparative linguistic study on verb classes in Uzbek and English. It examines the classification of mechanisms that means linking verbs to other verbs in English, while also identifying corresponding means of verb-linking in Uzbek in selected sections, focusing on their lexico-grammatical and structural properties. The analysis covers non-finite verb forms, including the gerund and infinitive, as well as phrasal and modal verbs, highlighting their combinability with other verbs. The article demonstrates how nominal features in non-finite forms influence verb combinations, while phrasal verbs and modal verbs contribute to the formation of [verb + verb] constructions. The article concludes that these linguistic means should be classified as distinct mechanisms facilitating verb-to-verb connections in English, reflecting both syntactic and semantic interactions within the verbal system.*

Keywords: *verb-to-verb linking, gerund, infinitive, phrasal verbs, modal verbs, non-finite verbs, English linguistics, Uzbek language, verbal constructions*

In order to classify the means linking verbs to verbs in both English and Uzbek languages, it is first necessary to clarify the essence of the term classification. Classification is a system of interrelated and similar concepts pertaining to a particular field of science or human activity. It is an essential logical operation inherent to every discipline, through which the knowledge accumulated within that field is systematically organized. It should be emphasized that classification facilitates the study of a particular discipline or object and simplifies the analytical process. When discussing classification, it is important to distinguish between its natural and artificial types. Natural classification is based on the essential features of the elements forming a set, whereas artificial classification relies on non-essential features.

Classifications in any field may change over time as knowledge expands. In other words, classifications constitute open systems that can be refined, expanded, or reduced. Classification is important because it enables concepts to become clearer in cognition and to be organized within a specific system. In other words, knowledge obtained as a result of classification is systematically arranged in thought. At this point, it is appropriate to note that the elements being classified share a common feature. The linking means, which constitute the object of our research, also share the common property of connecting one verb to another. However, it should also be noted that the means linking verbs to verbs are grouped into different categories and sets according to their specific features.

The means linking verbs to verbs in English, according to their lexico-grammatical and structural features, are grouped together with various linguistic units. Therefore, it is appropriate to analyze each of them separately. For example, the gerund form of the verb in English is studied within the morphological level, in the section devoted to the verb as a part of speech. In

this case, the gerund is included in the group of non-finite forms of the verb: “the gerund is a non-finite form of the verb which combines features characteristic of both the verb and the noun, and is formed by adding the suffix -ing to the verb” [1; 228-p.]. The nominal features of the gerund allow it to combine with verbs in the same way as a noun. In English-language sources, particular attention is also paid to the gerund forming constructions with other verbs [2; 204-p.]. The formation of combinations between the gerund and verbs of the verbal category is considered a phenomenon frequently observed in spoken English. In English, there are even verbs that specifically require a gerundial form to follow them, such as *to appreciate*, *to admit*, *to complete*, *to consider*, *to delay*, *to deny*, *to discuss*, *to dislike*, *to enjoy*, *to excuse*, *to fancy*, *to finish*, *to imagine*, *to keep*, *to mention*, *to mind*, *to miss*, *to postpone*, *to practise*, *to propose*, *to quit*, *to recall*, *to recommend*, *to regret*, *to report*, and others. Overall, the significance of the gerund in verb+verb constructions becomes particularly evident in contexts where clarification of a verb’s meaning is required through an action-related marker. For example, in the sentence “*Eating while reading is my habit*”, the necessity of using the gerund *eating* arises because one of the markers revealing the essence of the verb *reading* is related to an action. It should be noted that the gerund, as a form capable of linking one verb to another, has not been classified in English-language sources based on this specific function. Since this form of the verb possesses nominal characteristics, it is included in the group of non-finite verbal forms.

The infinitive form is also studied in English as a non-finite form of the verb. The infinitive is interpreted as the base form of the verb because it appears in texts in this form independently. According to some linguists, the infinitive is the form that has distanced itself from the most categorical features of the verb; it denotes an action but does not indicate its performer [3; 831-p.]. Linguists also emphasize that, due to the lack of person marking, interpreting the infinitive as a verb is sometimes considered incorrect. However, the meaning expressed by the infinitive (denoting an action) indicates that it should indeed be regarded as a verb. This is because the infinitive is distinguished as a verbal unit by its lexical meaning and by its use in combinations according to this meaning. Hence, Non-Finite verb forms are also frequently encountered in other languages. Furthermore, it should be emphasized that the infinitive’s inability to indicate person, and therefore its inability to function as a predicate in a sentence, does not affect its categorical features. The frequent use of the infinitive form within English constructions demonstrates its significant role in verbal combinability. The following verbs require the infinitive form of a verb to follow them: *to agree*, *to appear*, *to arrange*, *to ask*, *to claim*, *to consent*, *to decide*, *to demand*, *to deserve*, *to need*, *to offer*, *to plan*, *to desire*, *to prepare*, *to pretend*, *to expect*, *to promise*, *to fail*, *to refuse*, *to hesitate*, *to seem*, *to hope*, *to strive*, *to intend*, and others. Overall, the infinitive can combine with another verb both with or without the particle *to*. For example, in the sentences “*I saw her leave the school*” and “*I felt him put his hand on my hand*”, the infinitive is used without *to*, yet it serves to link the two verbs. It is thus evident that, according to its lexico-grammatical characteristics, the infinitive in English is studied alongside the gerund as a non-person-marking verb form. Its inability to indicate person allows the manifestation of nominal features. These nominal features also facilitate the combination of the infinitive with the governing verb in a construction.

Phrasal verbs can also combine with other verbs, as noted in English-language sources. As emphasized, phrasal verbs consist of a verb and a particle used as a lexical-semantic unit, and they express a unified figurative meaning similar to idiomatic expressions. Unlike idioms, however, phrasal verbs typically contain no more than one independent word. At this point, it is

necessary to highlight the division of phrasal verbs into transitive (open) and intransitive (closed) types. Intransitive (closed) phrasal verbs do not require the presence of any following element. They can be used simply in the verb+particle form. For example, in the sentence “*John passed out and we took him to the hospital*”, the phrasal verb *passed out* (to lose consciousness) does not require any specific element to follow it. Transitive (open) phrasal verbs, on the other hand, require a specific element to follow them [4; 983-p.] (in some cases, this element may itself be a verb). For example, in the sentence “*I have to put off our meeting until next week, because I have a conflict in my schedule*”, the phrasal verb *put off* requires the presence of a word that expresses the concept to be postponed.

Phrasal verbs are also classified according to the separability of the verb and the particle (i.e., the possibility of inserting a word between them). In inseparable phrasal verbs, it is not possible to place a word between the verb and the particle; in other words, the verb and the particle remain together. The sentence “*I am looking forward to seeing you*” provides examples of inseparable phrasal verbs. In contrast, in the sentence “*Put your hat on, it is cold outside*”, the phrasal verb *put on* includes the words *your hat* between the verb and the particle. Overall, since phrasal verbs are often used in a figurative sense, the verbal features of the verb involved may diminish or disappear. This, in turn, facilitates the combination of phrasal verbs with other verbs. Phrasal verbs are studied among verb constructions in English. Hence, in this context, represents a linguistic unit directly related to the combinability of the verbal category.

Modal verbs in English constitute a separate group of verbs expressing various modal meanings. As modal verbs are defective verbs, they do not exhibit all the forms present in full verbs. For example, “*can* and *may* possess only present and future tense forms (*can – could, may – might*), whereas modal verbs such as *must, need, and ought* to exist only in the present tense” [5; 364-p.]. As noted, the lack of a full independent meaning in modal verbs implies their use as non-autonomous predicates in [verb + verb] constructions. Therefore, it is methodologically appropriate to consider them not as means linking one verb to another, but as non-autonomous predicates within such constructions.

It should be emphasized that the means linking verbs to verbs have been thoroughly analyzed in English linguistics. These means have been studied as members of classifications related to the lexical and grammatical properties of the verbal category. For example, the infinitive and gerund forms of the verb “*decolorize*” the verbal features of the verb. These forms add nominal lexical and grammatical properties to the verbs they combine with. The manifestation of nominal lexical features in the gerund and infinitive is observed in the weakening of the “action” semantic feature and the strengthening of the “noun” semantic features, while changes in grammatical properties are reflected in the loss of person and number in verbs and, consequently, in the modification of their combinability. The formation of [verb + verb] constructions by phrasal verbs is facilitated, first, by their use together with particles, and second, by the figurative use of the verb and particle.

Without the properties mentioned, the formation of [verb + verb] constructions would be impossible. The combination of modal verbs with full-meaning verbs produces constructions analogous to the action-type forms in Uzbek. In our view, these means should be classified separately under the designation of means linking verbs to verbs.

Table: Classification of Means Linking Verbs to Verbs in English

No	Means Linking Verbs	Grammatical Status in English Linguistics	Example of Verb + Verb Construction
1	Infinitive	Non-finite verb form	need to sleep
2	Gerund	Non-finite verb form	eating while reading
3	Phrasal verbs	Verb combinations	give up smoking
4	Modal verbs	Defective verbs	I can do this work
5	Word (“and”)	Conjunction	They should finish and submit the report

In English, the means ensuring the combination of two verbs include the base form of the verb (infinitive), the gerund, phrasal verbs, modal verbs, particles, and conjunctions. Since constructions consisting of two verbs are not structurally standard in English, a verb is required to assume a specific form in order to combine with another verb.

In Uzbek linguistics, the grammatical properties of words belonging to the verb category have mainly been studied from the perspective of their functioning as the governing element in a sentence. Additionally, the means of linking verbs to other verbs have generally been systematized as part of the broader category of devices connecting linguistic units. Therefore, the classification of units that function as linking elements in constructions of the [verb + verb] pattern contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the characteristics of the verb category. In Uzbek, *converbial* (converb) and *participial* (participle) forms, which function as means of linking a verb to another verb, are studied within the framework of the *derivational category*. Case markers are treated as *relational forms of nouns*, while postpositions are analyzed as *auxiliary words*. Converbial and participial forms enable verbs to assume functions characteristic of adjectives and adverbs, thereby facilitating their combination with other verbs. For case markers and postpositions to link one verb to another, the verb must first occur in one of the derivational forms.

In summary, the study of means linking verbs to verbs in English reveals the intricate interplay between lexical, grammatical, and structural properties of the verbal system. Non-finite forms such as the gerund and infinitive demonstrate how nominal features influence verb combinability, while phrasal verbs and modal verbs further extend the capacity for [verb + verb] constructions. The analysis underscores that these linguistic mechanisms, through their specific semantic and syntactic characteristics, play a central role in English verbal combinations. Accordingly, recognizing and classifying these forms as distinct means linking verbs to verbs provides a clearer understanding of English verb system functionality and contributes to the broader field of English linguistics.

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